

Studies on catechu : Isolation of (+)-catechin from different parts of *Acacia catechu*

M. Y. Ali^{a*}, M. U. Ali^b and M. A. Hye^b

^aGreen University of Bangladesh, Farmgate, Dhaka-1215, Bangladesh

E-mail : aliyusuffm@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Rajshahi University, Rajshahi-6205, Bangladesh

Manuscript received 23 April 2007, revised 28 August 2007, accepted 6 September 2007

Abstract : A convenient method for isolation of (+)-catechin from *A. catechu* Willd. has been suggested. (+)-Catechin content of different parts of the tree and effect of storage time on (+)-catechin content has also been reported.

Keywords : *Acacia catechu*, leguminosae, catechu, (+)-catechin.

Catechu (Cutch, gilla variety) is a hot water extract of the red heart wood of *Acacia catechu* Willd. Catechu is produced in cottage industries in the northern part of Bangladesh. It is also produced in large quantities in India and Burma¹. Catechu is generally used with betel leaf for chewing and in the tanneries for leather tanning^{2,3}. Its therapeutic use has been declined tremendously with the rapid development of synthetic drugs². Catechu is also used for dyeing sails and nets because of its rot proofing quality². Faruk *et al.* developed a method for applying catechu brown dye for dyeing cotton and silk fabrics⁴.

The main constituents of catechu are (+)-catechin and catechutannic acid with small proportion of brown colouring matter⁵. It is valued for its catechin content which is the effective ingredient of edible as well as medicinal catechu⁶. Catechin is the *trans* and epicatechin is the *cis*-isomer⁷. Works have been reported on extraction, composition and use of catechu but (+)-catechin content of different parts of *Acacia catechu* tree has not been reported⁵⁻⁹. Ali *et al.* isolated catechin from catechu by a lengthy and laborious process¹⁰. Hence, it might be of

interest (i) to develop a convenient method for isolation of (+)-catechin from *A. catechu* tree, (ii) to study the (+)-catechin content in different parts of the tree and (iii) to investigate the effect of storage time on the (+)-catechin content of the red heart wood.

Results and discussion

When the small chips of red heart wood were extracted with boiling water for 4 h, the extract evaporated to a highly saturated solution and allowed to stand for 24 h, a thick sedimentation settled down. It was dissolved in ethanol, filtered, evaporated and reprecipitated from water thrice. The product (yield, 3.75% w/w) was obtained as almost a colorless powder. It was dried in a vacuum desiccator over P₂O₅, m.p. 176°. The R_f values (tlc, pc) and mixed m.p. of the isolated catechin were in good agreement with the authentic sample. The isolated compound is soluble in hot water and alcohol giving reddish brown and bright pink color respectively. It showed positive color reaction with ferric chloride. It also responded to specific color reactions of flavonoids¹¹.

Table 1

Sl. no.	Layers	Wood (g)	% (w/w)	Quantity of Catechu (g)	% of Catechu	% of Catechu on the basis of total catechu	% of Catechin from catechu
1.	Outer most layers	960	5.4	25.3	2.6	0.97	—
2.	Inner bark	2240	12.8	475.3	21.2	18.3	6.35
3.	Sap wood	4520	25.8	439.0	9.7	16.9	7.50
4.	Red heart wood	9740	55.7	1655.8	17.0	63.8	25.0

Note

(+)-Catechin (**1**) was identified by comparison of its spectral data (IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR) with literature as well as preparation of its pentamethyl ether and pentabenzoyl ester¹².

Isolation of catechu and (+)-catechin was done on different layers of the stem, such as outermost bark, inner bark, sap wood, red heart wood and also of the leaves as in the preceding experiment and is shown in the Table 1.

Maximum catechu (17%) was isolated from the red heart wood while only traces were found in the outer layer. Catechu content of inner bark and sap wood was not significant. The (+)-catechin content of the red heart wood, however, is maximum (25%) while those of inner bark and sap wood was poor (6.35% and 7.50%). Extraction and isolation from the leaves afforded 40% catechu and 10% (+)-catechin.

Work was extended to investigate (+)-catechin content of the red heart wood of *A. catechu* with storage time prior to extraction, as harvesting, transportation to the site and preparation of chips needed considerable time. Effect of storage time was studied using two parameters in which the chips or the wood were stored for certain days. Results are shown in the Table 2.

Apparently, long storage time did not have pronounced effect on the catechu content as the decay of catechu content even after 120 days was insignificant. Decay of (+)-catechin content was significant as the red heart wood lost 20–24% (+)-catechin in 45 days and loss was rapid

after 45 days. However, decay of (+)-catechin was comparatively rapid when the chips were stored for long time. These observations manifest polymerization of (+)-catechin to lignins and tannin after harvesting the tree.

Experimental

Isolation of (+)-catechin: The red heart wood of *Acacia catechu* tree were cut into small chips. The dried chips (1 kg) were boiled with 4 litres of water for 4 h and filtered through a fine cloth. (+)-Catechin precipitated on standing. The extracted catechu was dissolved in a litre of boiled water, filtered hot and concentrated to 500 ml. After standing overnight, the precipitated substance was filtered out, dissolved in ethanol and filtered again. The clear solution was evaporated to dryness, dissolved again in 500 ml hot water and filtered. On standing the solution overnight (+)-catechin was obtained. It was dried over P_2O_5 in a desiccator, m.p. 176° . Yield 45 g, 25% (w/w catechu), 3.75% (w/w dry wood). Thin layer chromatography of the isolated (+)-catechin on a silica gel 60G plate using toluene : ethyl acetate : formic acid (10 : 8 : 1) solvent system gave a single spot (R_f 0.27). Paper chromatography of the isolated (+)-catechin using isopropyl alcohol : H_2O (22 : 78) (descending) and spraying the paper with 1% ferric chloride gave a single spot R_f 0.65; IR ν_{max} 3500–3150 (broad), 1620, 1470, 1380, 1290, 1250, 1115, 1050, 1030 and 832 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, acetone- d_6) δ_{TMS} 4.56 (H-2, dd, $J_{(\text{H}-2, \text{H}-3\text{a})}$ 7.8 Hz), 4.00 (H-3, dd, $J_{(\text{H}-3\text{a}, \text{H}-4\text{e})}$ 5.58 Hz, $J_{(\text{H}-3\text{a}, \text{H}-4\text{a})}$ 8.5 Hz, $J_{(\text{H}-3\text{a}, \text{H}-2\text{a})}$ 7.8 Hz), 2.54 (H-4a, dd, $J_{(\text{H}-4\text{a}, \text{H}-3\text{a})}$ 8.5 Hz, $J_{(\text{H}-4\text{a}, \text{H}-4\text{c})}$ 16.1 Hz), 2.90 (H-4e, $J_{(\text{H}-4\text{c}, \text{H}-3\text{a})}$ 5.58 Hz, $J_{(\text{H}-4\text{e}, \text{H}-4\text{a})}$ 16.1 Hz), 5.87 (H-6, d, $J_{(\text{H}-6, \text{H}-8)}$ 2.3 Hz), 6.02 (H-8, d, $J_{(\text{H}-8, \text{H}-6)}$ 2.3 Hz), 6.89 (H-2', d, $J_{(\text{H}-2', \text{H}-6')}$ 1.95 Hz), 6.79 (H-5', d, $J_{(\text{H}-5', \text{H}-6')}$ 8.1 Hz), 6.73 (H-6', dd, $J_{(\text{H}-6', \text{H}-2')}$ 1.95 Hz, $J_{(\text{H}-6', \text{H}-5')}$ 8.1 Hz) and 8.0 (phenolic protons, m); ^{13}C NMR (500 MHz) δ_{TMS} 27.74 (C-4), 66.52 (C-3), 80.96 (C-2), 95.2 (C-6), 93.91 (C-8), 99.1 (C-10),

Table 2

Storage time in days	Chips		Decay %	Wood		
	% of Catechu	% of (+)-Catechin		% of Catechu	% of (+)-Catechin	Decay %
5	18.60	3.8		17.91	3.75	
15	18.54	3.4	11	18.20	3.20	14.66
30	18.61	3.0	21	18.40	3.10	17.33
45	18.45	2.9	24	18.41	3.00	20
60	18.60	2.4	37	17.09	2.50	33.4
90	18.50	1.5	61	18.50	1.45	61.4
120	18.59	0.8	79	18.60	0.60	84
140	18.63	0.2	95	17.95	0.23	93.9

115.11 (C-2'), 114.51 (C-5'), 118.41 (C-6'), 130.64 (C-1'), 144.81 (C-3'), 144.81 (C-4'), 155.33 (C-7), 156.42 (C-5), 156.14 (C-9).

Tetramethyl ether (m.p. 145°) and pentabenzoyl ester (m.p. 172°) of (+)-catechin were prepared using standard methods¹³.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support from Third World Network of Scientific Organizations, Trieste, Italy and the Ministry of Science, Information and Communication Technology, Government of People's Republic of Bangladesh. The spectra were registered by the courtesy of H. E. J. Research Institute of Chemistry, University of Karachi, Pakistan.

References

1. *Bull. Imp. Inst., London*, 1930, **28**, 433.
2. S. S. Bhatnagar (ed.), "The Wealth of India", CSIR, India, 1948, p. 19.
3. G. Watt, "A Dictionary of Economic Products of India", International Book Distributors, Dehra Dun, India, 1972, **1**, 41.
4. M. O. Faruk, R. K. Sarker and M. E. Haque, *Bangladesh J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1979, **14**, 69.
5. M. H. Khundkar, *Science and Industry*, 1964, **2**, 309.
6. C. P. Sharma, "Chemistry and Technology of Katha Manufacturing", International Book Distributors, Dehra Dun, India, 1984, p. 86.
7. R. C. Elderfield, "Heterocyclic Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, 1963, **2**, 359.
8. M. S. Ali, M. B. Zaman, M. N. Islam and I. H. Mandal, *Bangladesh J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1982, **17**, 126.
9. M. S. Ali, M. A. Hye, M. I. H. Mandal and M. A. Rahman, *Bangladesh J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1991, **26**, 171.
10. M. S. Ali, R. K. Sarker, M. A. Hye, M. I. H. Mandal, M. Rahman, M. A. Ahsan and M. A. Rahman, *Bangladesh J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1993, **28**, 146.
11. J. B. Harborne, "Biochemistry of Phenolic Compounds", Academic Press, 1964, p. 46.
12. Personal Communication from H. E. J. Research Institute of Chemistry, University of Karachi, Pakistan.
13. I. Heilbron, A. H. Cook, H. M. Bunbury and D. H. Hey, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", London, 1965, **1**, 572.